

PURPOSE, TASKS AND BASIC CONCEPTS OF THE DATABASE

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Abstract. This article describes the database and the main terms of the database, as well as the requirements for the database and automated information systems.

Key word: database, information system, automated information system, structuring, base, technology.

НАЗНАЧЕНИЕ, ЗАДАЧИ И ОСНОВНЫЕ ПОНЯТИЯ БАЗЫ ДАННЫХ

Аннотация. В данной статье описывается база данных и основные термины базы данных, а также требования к базе данных автоматизированных информационных систем.

Ключевые слова: база данных, информационная система, автоматизированная информационная система, структурирование, база, технология.

When creating a database, the user tries to sort the information by various characters and quickly get a selection with an arbitrary combination of characters. This can only be done if the data is structured. Structuring is the introduction of an agreement on how to represent data. If there is no agreement on how to represent information, then it is unstructured. An example of unstructured data is data written to a text file. Users of the database can use various practical applications, software tools, and specialists in the field of the subject. A subject area is a certain part of the real environment that is studied to organize the work of an automated other. For example, an enterprise, a factory, a scientific research institute, a university, etc. Data is a set of arbitrary symbols that are used regardless of their meaning. Interrelated information is called an information system. A database is a named collection of systematic information related to a specific subject area, written in computer memory in a certain structure, linked and ordered. It is a data set. it expresses in a certain sense the property, state or relationship between objects. MB provides the user with optimal convenience in storing and using structured information. It is known that the process of entering and processing data is a large-scale work that requires a lot of work and time. When working with MB, the bot work with a clear structure of the data in it, firstly, it makes it easier for the user to enter and sort the data in the process of processing, and secondly, to search for the necessary data and quickly extract it. Before the concept of MB entered science, it was very difficult to use data in different ways. Today, the issue of using and processing data of various types in modern computers has been solved. MB stored on computers is a file with a special format, rich in a specific structure, and the information in it is interconnected and sorted. A database is a set of data stored in a specific structure. In other words, MB is a file with a special format that contains information with a specific structure. Data structuring is simply a way of introducing some consistency in data representation. Usually, MB represents a specific object area and contains linking data, stores them and allows the user to use it in data processing. The database is the main component of information systems. Database management systems are created to facilitate the user's work in working with the database. These systems separate the database from

the application programs. A database management system (DBMS) is a complex set of software and hardware tools that allow a user to create a database and work on the data in this database.

The main elements of the database structure: Field *uri - it is expressed by the fact that the entered record belongs to a certain type. For example, it can be numeric, character, date/time, integer, logical, etc. The length of the field is the sum of the characters of the text in the field. A record is a collection of logically related fields. The structure of the record is determined by the composition and location sequence of the fields included in it, and each of them is called a copy of the elementary records. A record represents complete information about an element of an object. An object (table) is a set of copies of a record with the same structure. It has a value in each field. For example, the logical structure of records in the student object is shown in the example. The structure of a record in a student file is linear, consisting of fixed-length records. Record fields do not have repeating groups of values. Reference to the value of the area is made by its number.

Each MB table can have its own primary key. A primary key is defined as a field or group of fields that ensures that it cannot be written back. A field or group of fields used as a primary key must satisfy the condition that it does not have a single xii variable. The same entries can be repeated in other fields. Therefore, they cannot be primary keys. It is desirable that the primary key consists of short and numerical fields. The purpose of entering a primary key in the MB table is to provide convenience in searching, sorting and selecting the data in the table. Whether or not to include a primary key is defined by the user when creating the MB table structure. A foreign key is created in another table to ensure that the corresponding data in the other table can be called using the main table. In the case of a "one-to-many" relationship, the foreign key is created in the parent table. When defining the first and second cases, MBBT automatically builds an index in the table. When solving specific information (problem), a person is limited to one or another area of the real world. In such cases, I am interested in studying only some objects. Such a complex of objects is called an object field. All objects are characterized by attributes. For example, faculty, library, computer and administration can be considered as objects. Including the speed of calculation as an attribute of the computer object. you can see RAM size, dimensions, etc. The smallest unit of data is a data element. Lee is often said to be square and bay! and consists of bits. A data set is a named collection of data items. MB administrators are the individuals or groups of individuals responsible for the design, transmission, and effective operation of MB. With the concept of a database, there is also the concept of a data bank. The concept of data bank (MBn) is interpreted in two ways. 1. Currently, data is processed in a decentralized manner (in workers' offices) with the help of SHK. Previously, they were processed centrally in data centers located in isolated rooms. Information is collected in computing centers through different devices. Due to the fact that the database is centralized, they are called data banks. In this case, the reference to the data is created centrally from workstations, and therefore the concepts of a data bank and a database are differentiated. Nowadays, in most cases, the database is not organized in a decentralized manner. Therefore, the data bank and database are also used as synonyms. 2. In another interpretation, a database is understood as a database management system (MBBT). A program that works with a database is called an application. One data can work a lot with the database. Advantages of using MB: - compactness; - increase in data processing speed; - low labor cost; - possibility to always get new information;
- reduction of data redundancy.

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